

PILOT TESTS

In Real Port Environments

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Elefsina

📍 Elefsis Port, Greece

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Figure: USV performing a rapid hull scan

From Research to Innovative Results

To ensure close collaboration between the project end users (security agencies and port authorities) and the technical partners throughout the project lifecycle, SMAUG will showcase and validate the multiple solutions developed during the project in 3 pilots. These will be executed, and their outcomes will be evaluated in a real port environment, specifically at the ports of Valencia (Spain), Elefsina (Greece), Heraklion (Greece), and Drammen (Norway).

- Pilot Summary

Elefsis Port

Our partners from the University of Piraeus Research Centre & the Elefsis Port Authority are sharing the collective insights and updates on the technical validations conducted so far regarding **Aerial and Underwater Detection**.

Figure: Matrice 4E drone with its carrying case

Underwater Detection in Elefsis Port

Regarding underwater detection in Elefsina, two main technologies were deployed during the pre-pilot phase. First, the hydrophone array consisting of three hydrophones was installed within the pilot area, at approximately one meter below the water surface. The system was connected to an audio interface and a Raspberry Pi running UPM's scripts for data upload to the broker, while connectivity was ensured via 5G (mobile hotspot). Hardware setup and data transmission operated successfully, providing the basis for validating underwater acoustic measurements.

In parallel, a sonar-based approach was tested. Initial trials focused on verifying the USV's stable navigation and controller performance. Following these validations, the sonar was mounted on the USV to conduct a rapid hull scan.

Figure: Hydrophone system overview

A subsequent test involved attaching the same sonar to the ROV, enabling a high-definition inspection that successfully detected the mock-up suspicious object. The main technical challenge identified, concerned seamless communication with the sonar while installed on the USV.

Figure: Visualization of sonar output

Figure: Image and data visualisation displayed on the ROV controller

Figure: ROV with sonar attached

Aerial Detection

Regarding aerial detection in Elefsina, the drone system conducted continuous patrol flights over the designated pilot area to detect suspicious vessel movements. During these operations, the embedded AI-based vessel recognition feature was employed to support visual detection in real time, through the operator's controller interface. Prior to deployment, all required flight permissions were secured and coordination with the nearby airport control tower ensured safe integration of drone activities within the controlled airspace.

AI acquisition & Data integration

Regarding data acquisition, several actions are planned to be carried out in order to ensure proper integration and management of the information generated by the different systems.

The data management platform (including the Broker, API, RTSP server, and related components) is in ongoing development by FAVIT. The system will run on the port server, and the necessary services will be prepared to support the use case. A data display interface will also be configured to visualise the information received from each connected device.

The AIS system, implemented by ATHANOR, will be installed at the port facility and connected to the local area network (LAN). It will be integrated with FAVIT's data platform, followed by a functional test to validate the operation of the complete data chain.

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